

DHX58 (aka LGP2)

(DExH-box helicase 58)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

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SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a debilitating neurodegenerative disorder that affects more than 7 million Americans aged 65 and older [1]. To date, there is no known effective treatment for AD. The past two decades of AD drug discovery efforts have focused on a limited number of therapeutic hypotheses and have resulted in little success in developing transformative human therapies. To address the poorly populated clinical pipeline, the National Institute on Aging launched the TREAT-AD (TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for AD) initiative, which aims to expand and diversify the portfolio of AD drug targets through accelerating the characterization and experimental validation of novel therapeutic targets. One of these potential targets, the DHX58 helicase, was nominated by TREAT-AD due to its potential role in driving AD progression (<https://agora.adknowledgeportal.org/genes>). DHX58 (encoding the LGP2 protein) is a member of the DExH-box family of helicases, specifically within the RIG-1 subfamily. It employs ATP hydrolysis to drive its binding to nucleic acids and to regulate MDA5–RNA interactions related to the activation of the innate immune response to viral RNA [2]. As part of TREAT-AD, we aim to generate Target Enabling Packages (TEPs) for our nominated targets, which include methods for protein purification and the development of biochemical and biophysical assays that enable small molecule chemical probe discovery. These tools and reagents presented here will facilitate the further evaluation of the role of DHX58/LGP2 in AD progression and its potential value as a drug target for the treatment of AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

DExH-box helicase 58 (DHX58), a gene encoding protein LGP2, is a member of the RIG-1-like receptor subfamily of helicases, which also includes RIG-1 and IFIH1. These helicases play a role in the innate immune response, which is driven by their recognition of and binding to viral RNA [3–5]. Unlike RIG-1 and IFIH1 (a gene encoding protein MDA5), LGP2 does not contain N-terminal caspase recruitment domains (CARDs), which are critical to the helicase's ability to interact with mitochondrial antiviral-signaling (MAV) proteins [6]. LGP2 therefore lacks signaling ability alone, and is rather thought to behave as an innate immune sensor that promotes the binding of other helicases, such as MDA5, to viral RNA [7,8]. The presence of LGP2 within this interaction is necessary, given that MDA5 itself does not have strong binding affinity to dsRNA. The role of LGP2 is believed to be in initiating and stabilizing the formation of MDA5 oligomeric filaments along the dsRNA, which then interact with MAVs through their clustered CARD domains to trigger downstream an interferon and pro-inflammatory responses related to innate immune activation [2,7].

Given the high relevance of overactive immune and inflammatory signaling to the pathogenesis and progression of AD, a therapeutic target that acts as a key regulator of the innate immune response offers an attractive approach to potentially addressing the disease [9]. Beyond the broadly pro-inflammatory environment observed in the AD brain, there are specific hypotheses which pose that aberrant activation of

the innate immune response may be playing a significant role in disease progress [10]. Indeed, studies have proposed that it is specifically the amyloid beta fibrils that contain nucleic acids (such as dsRNA) that are found to lead to synaptic loss, due to the type I interferon response that they trigger [11]. As LGP2 represents a key link between presence of nucleic acids and the activation of this immune response, the modulation of DHX58/LGP2 could have beneficial effects in interrupting the hyper-neuroinflammatory state characteristic of AD.

BIOINFORMATIC ANALYSIS

Target Source & Hypothesis

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [12]. Gene set enrichment analysis of all scored genes highlights the "innate immune response" Gene Ontology (GO) term as one of the most significantly enriched among genes with the highest Target Risk Score. This GO term was also identified through analysis of transcriptomic and proteomic pseudotime states [13] as being among the processes for which there is evidence of differential expression in early states of disease progression. Among the leading edge (i.e. top-scoring) genes in the "innate immune response" GO term were a set of RNA helicase proteins including IFIH1, DHX58, and DDX1. Network pathway modeling identified these as central nodes within the network related to innate immune response, and analysis of patient pseudotime indicates the expression of these genes changes in early disease pseudo-states. These targets were nominated within a hypothesis that over-activation of the innate immune response triggers aberrant cytokine signaling and excessive phagocytosis of synapses and neurons, leading to neurodegenerative pathogenesis in AD.

DHX58 has a TREAT-AD Target Risk Score of 2.63 out of 5 (rank #7260, 70.9th percentile) (**Fig. 1A**). The individual score components include 1.8 of 3 (79th percentile) for genetics (**Fig. 1B**), and 0.827 out of 2 (55.6th percentile) for genomics (**Fig. 1C**). The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of DHX58 protein is not detected and RNA is significantly lower in brains from patients with AD.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD) (sea-ad.org, [14]). Gene expression was averaged across cells within a supertype from each donor. The locally weighted mean expression (LOWESS) of superotypes within each subclass is then plotted across the range of continuous donor pseudo-progression, which orders subjects based on a learned model of neuropathological burden. DHX58 is expressed primarily in Astrocyte, Endothelial, and Microglia cell types from the SEA-AD dataset (**Fig. 1D**). DHX58 expression is stable within cell types subclasses across donor pseudo-progression.

Figure 1. (A) TREAT-AD Target Risk Score, (B) component genetic risk score and (C) multi-omic risk score for DHX58. The lines within the score and component score violin plots show the 50th and 90th percentile scores. (D) DHX58 cell-type expression data from SEA-AD. Cell type expression plots show the locally weighted mean expression of cell supertypes from each donor within each subclass along donor pseudo-progression.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains) [12]. These biodomains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biodomains via GO term annotations. DHX58 is annotated to GO terms from 3 biodomain(s), primarily to terms from the Immune Response, RNA Spliceosome, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domain(s) (Fig. 2A).

The CRISPRbrain resource (crisprbrain.org, [15]) is a data commons for functional genomics datasets from differentiated human iPSC derived cell types. The resource reports phenotype results following CRISPR screens of gene activation (CRISPRa), inhibition (CRISPRi), or gene knockout (CRISPRn), in iPSC derived brain-relevant cell types. Following the screens, genes are identified as either positive or negative hits, meaning perturbation leads to a significant and reproducible increase or decrease in the measured phenotype, respectively, or a non-hit if the perturbation does not significantly impact the phenotype. DHX58 is not a hit in any assay (Fig. 2B).

Figure 2. (A) DHX58 TREAT-AD biological domain annotations and **(B)** phenotypes from CRISPR screens in iPSC derived cell types from the CRISPRbrain resource.

PROTEIN CONSTRUCTS AND EXPRESSION METHODS

Proteins Purified

1. **Full-length Biotinylated & His-tagged LGP2 (FL-LGP2):** Full-length construct (aa1-678) of human LGP2. Contains an N-terminal AviTag biotinylation signal and C-terminal His6 tag. Protein produced in sf9 insect cells. Used in ATPase assay and SPR.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

BIOCHEMICAL ASSAYS

ATPase Activity Assay

While helicases typically use ATP hydrolysis to unwind RNA duplexes, LGP2 instead couples it to conformational changes that drive RNA binding and release [2]. Here, we developed a high-throughput ATPase activity assay to screen for compounds that inhibit the ATPase activity of LGP2 (**Fig. 3A, B**) [16]. The assay uses a 24-mer dsRNA (GGGACGUCAUGCGCAUGACGUCCC) from IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies, USA) as a substrate and measures the level of leftover ATP in each reaction using the Kinase-Glo reagent (Promega, Cat#

V6712; Promega, Madison, WI, USA). The reaction mixtures contained 4 μ M ATP and 100 nM of 24-mer dsRNA in 20 mM Tris–HCl buffer (pH 7.5, 0.01% Tween 20, 1 mM MgCl₂, and 2 mM DTT), with a final volume of 15 μ L per well. The reactions were initiated by adding LGP2 at a final concentration of 100 nM. The reaction mixtures were incubated for 30–60 min and then quenched by adding 15 μ L of luciferase reagent mix to each well. Subsequently, 25 μ L of the mixture from each well was transferred to a 384-well white detection plate and incubated for an additional 15 min before measuring luminescence signals using a BioTek Synergy 4 plate reader. The data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism 8. We also determined the Z'-factor for the LGP2 ATPase assay, showing that this assay is amenable for high-throughput screening (**Fig. 3C**).

Figure 3. LGP2 ATPase activity assay for compound screening. (A) Schematic overview of ATPase activity assay. (B) Km determinations for 24-mer RNA with LGP2. The addition of 24mer-RNA promotes LGP2 ATPase activity in a concentration dependent manner. (C) Z'-factor determination for LGP2. The activity RLU without LGP2 (●) and with LGP2 (■) wells. Z'-factor calculated as previously described [17].

CONCLUSION

DHX58, a RIG-1-like receptor subfamily helicase gene encoding the protein LGP2, was selected as an AD target based on genetic and genomic data, which was used to generate an integrative AD target ranking score presented in the report above. DHX58 was annotated with TREAT-AD-defined GO biodomains related to immune response, RNA Spliceosome, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis. RNA expression of DHX58 is reduced in brains from AD patients, while protein was not detected in our analyses. Though the predicted therapeutic directionality of DHX58 modulation is unknown, we have developed novel tools and reagents to promote the further investigation into the roles of this protein in AD. First, we generated full-length DHX58 constructs for the purification of the LGP2 protein. With this full-length protein in hand, we developed a LGP2 ATPase biochemical assay and used surface plasmon resonance (SPR) for biophysical characterization of small molecule binding. Generation of these materials will facilitate the development of small molecule chemical probes aimed at LGP2 for future in vitro and in vivo investigations.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. Full length Biotinylated & His-tagged LGP2

Sample ID	PBC037-B05
Purpose	ATPase assay & SPR
Vector	pFBD-BirA
AA start to end	1-678
N-terminal tag	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
C-terminal tag	GGSGHHHHHH
Expected Mass (Da)	80196.63
Protein sequence	MSGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGMELRSYQWEVIMPALEGKNIWLP TGAAGKTRAAAYVAKRHLETVDGAKVVVVLNVRVHLVTQHGEEFR RMLDGRWTVTTLSGDMGPRAGFGHLARCHDLLICTAELLQ MALTSPEEEHVELTVFSLIVVDECHHTHKDVTYVNVIMS QYLELKLQRAQPLPQVLGLTASPGTGGASKLDGAINHVL QLCANLDTWCIMSPQNCCPQLQEHSQQPCKQYNLCHRR SQDPFGDLLKKLMDQIHDHLEMPELSRKFGTQMYEQQV VKLSEAAALAGLQEQRVYALHLRRYNDALLIHDTVRAV DALAALQDFYHREHVTKTQILCAERRLLALFDDRKNEL AHLATHGPENPKLEMLEKILQRQFSSNSPRGIIFTRTR QSAHLLLWLQQQGLQTVDIRAQLLIGAGNSSQSTHMTQR DQQEVIQKFQDGTLNLLVATSVAEEGLDIPHCNVVVRY GLLTNEISMVQARGRARADQSVYAFVATEGSRELKREL INEALETLMQAVAAVQKMDQAEYQAKIRDLOQAALTK RAAQAAQRENQRQQFPVEHVQLLCINCMVAVGHGSD LRKVEGTHHVNVNPNFSNYNVSRDPVVINKVFKDWK PGGVISCRCGEVWGLQMIYKSVKLPVLKVRSMLETPQ GRIQAKKWSRVPFSPDFDFLQHCAENLSDLSLDGG SGHHHHHH

Purified protein (PBC037B05)	
<p>IMAC, Ni-NTA (step 1):</p>	<p>Ni-NTA profile.</p> <p>From 6L culture, 3mL beads/L culture. W1: Lysis b., W2: 1M NaCl, W3: Imi30mM, E3 to E5 for SEC.</p>
<p>SEC (step 2):</p>	<p>GF profile.</p> <p>Collected: E4 to F4</p>
<p>Intact mass deconvolution (Da):</p>	<p>Full Range</p> <p>80336</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>5.7 mg/L culture</p>

<p>Expression and purification protocol</p>	<p>The wild-type gene of LGP2 (1-678aa) was PCR amplified and subcloned into pFBD-BirA vector. Proteins were expressed in Sf9 insect cells using biotin-supplemented media and harvested 72-96 h post-infection following a previously reported protocol [18]. Harvested cells were resuspended in 20 mM Tris-HCL, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1X protease inhibitor cocktail (100 X protease inhibitor stock in 70% ethanol (0.25 mg/mL Aprotinin, 0.25 mg/mL Leupeptin, 0.25 mg/mL Pepstatin A and 0.25 mg/mL E-64). The cells were lysed chemically with 0.5% NP40 and benzonase (in-house), followed by sonication at frequency of 7.0 (5" on/7" off) for 2 min (Sonicator 3000, Misoni). The crude extract was clarified by high-speed centrifugation at 14000 rpm for 60 min at 10 °C by Beckman Coulter centrifuge. The clarified lysate was passed through an open column containing equilibrated Ni-NTA resins. The column was first washed with 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 5 mM imidazole. A second wash with the same buffer containing 1 M NaCl and 5 mM imidazole was performed to remove bound nucleic acids. A third wash with 30 mM imidazole and 500 mM NaCl was applied, and the target protein was finally eluted with 250 mM imidazole in the same buffer. The eluted protein was supplemented with 1mM TCEP and further purified by size-exclusion chromatography on a Superdex200 26/60 column using an ÄKTA Pure (Cytiva) system with a running buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 1 mM TCEP.</p>
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